

ISO 9001 Certifications Worldwide

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The variable "ISO 9001 quality certificates/bn PPP\$ GDP" represents the number of ISO 9001 quality certificates per billion of GDP expressed in terms of Purchasing Power Parity (PPP). ISO 9001 certificates refer to those issued in a specific country or region, and they attest that an organization has implemented a quality management system compliant with international standards. GDP in PPP dollars accounts for differences in purchasing power between countries, allowing for fairer comparisons across price levels. In summary, this variable measures the diffusion of ISO 9001 quality certificates in relation to the economic size of a country, providing insights into how widely these certificates are adopted relative to the economic value expressed in billions of international PPP dollars. This indicator is useful for comparing the adoption of ISO 9001 certifications across economies of different scales. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Global ISO 9001 Certifications in 2022 show significant variations in the number of ISO 9001 certificates per billion PPP dollars of GDP among countries, indicating different levels of adoption of this quality standard relative to each country's economic size. ISO 9001 is a globally recognized standard for quality management systems, adopted by many organizations in various sectors to demonstrate their ability to provide products and services that meet regulatory and customer needs. The ratio between the number of certificates and GDP adjusted for PPP allows us to compare the adoption of this standard more homogeneously across countries with different economic scales. At the top of the ranking is Italy, with a value of 100 ISO 9001 quality certificates per billion PPP dollars of GDP. This suggests a strong adoption of the standard by Italian organizations, highlighting a high level of attention to quality and process certification. It is noteworthy that although Italy has a developed economy, its strong presence in sectors such as manufacturing, agri-food, and the automotive industry, all highly regulated and focused on quality, may explain this figure. The culture of certification in Italy is well-established, with many companies seeing ISO 9001 as a prerequisite to compete in international markets. Following closely behind are Bulgaria and Belarus, with 97.2 and 97 certificates per billion PPP dollars of GDP, respectively. Despite having smaller economies compared to more developed countries, these numbers indicate a significant focus on quality. It is likely that in these countries, ISO 9001 is seen as an important tool to attract investment and improve access to global markets. For Bulgaria, as a member of the European Union, compliance with

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international standards is likely viewed as a strategy to integrate more effectively with Western markets. Other Eastern European countries, such as Serbia, the Czech Republic, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Croatia, also show high levels of ISO 9001 certification relative to their GDP, with values ranging from 63 to 57.8. This could reflect these countries' desire to align with European and international regulations in anticipation of commercial expansion or deeper integration with the European Union, particularly in the cases of Serbia and Bosnia-Herzegovina. ISO 9001 certification represents a quality assurance that can help companies in these regions compete more effectively in the European and global markets. Looking at Western Europe, countries such as Germany, the United Kingdom, and France, despite being among the world's largest and most developed economies, show relatively lower values in terms of ISO 9001 adoption per billion PPP dollars of GDP. Germany, for instance, has a value of 28.1, the United Kingdom 22.7, and France 18.5. These lower values can be explained by the fact that in advanced economies, numerous other sector-specific or niche certifications may be preferred by companies. Additionally, in these countries, the perception of quality may already be deeply ingrained in production and management processes, reducing the need to demonstrate compliance through external certifications. Among non-European countries, China stands out with a value of 34.5, which, although lower than in many European countries, is significant given the vastness of its economy. This figure suggests that China is rapidly adopting international quality standards, likely to improve the reputation of its products globally and ensure access to foreign markets. The strong expansion of the Chinese manufacturing sector has led many companies to seek to enhance their competitiveness by adopting quality management systems like ISO 9001. Countries such as Brazil, Argentina, and Chile, with values between 16.5 and 14.3, also show a certain level of ISO 9001 certification adoption, though not to the extent seen in Europe or some Asian countries. In these emerging economies, ISO 9001 may be seen as an opportunity to improve quality and competitiveness in global markets, although diffusion may be hindered by economic or structural factors. The United States, with a value of 2.2, represents a unique case. Despite having the largest economy in the world, the low number of ISO 9001 certificates per billion PPP dollars of GDP can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, in the United States, many other sector-specific certifications, such as AS9100 for aerospace or IATF 16949 for the automotive industry, may be preferred by companies. Additionally, the culture of quality in the United States may be less tied to formal ISO 9001 certification and more oriented toward internal or industry-specific standards. In Africa and many developing economies, values are generally low, such as in Nigeria (0.5), Angola (0.9), or Ethiopia (0), suggesting that ISO 9001 certification is not yet widely adopted. Economic barriers, lack of infrastructure, and the cost of certification may be among the main obstacles. However, in some of these economies, the growing international demand for quality standards may lead to increased adoption of ISO 9001 certification in the future. Overall, the data highlight that the adoption of ISO 9001 varies significantly between countries and regions. In European countries, particularly in Eastern Europe, there is greater attention to ISO 9001 certification compared to Western European countries, which may reflect the need to demonstrate compliance with international standards to access foreign markets. Emerging economies, such as China and Brazil, are adopting ISO 9001 certification as a tool to improve their reputation and competitiveness. However, in many developing economies, the diffusion of this standard is still limited, likely due to economic and infrastructural challenges. In summary, ISO 9001 remains an important indicator of quality for many companies worldwide, but its level of adoption varies considerably depending on the region and the economic structure of different countries.

Global ISO 9001 Certifications Between 2013 and 2022. The data show significant variation in the adoption of ISO 9001 quality certificates between 2013 and 2022 across different countries. The main indicator that emerges is the absolute and percentage change in certificates issued relative to GDP,

revealing very different trends across countries, with some showing impressive growth and others experiencing sharp declines. Belarus stands out as an exceptional case, with a dramatic increase in the number of ISO 9001 certificates, rising from 2.4 in 2013 to 97 in 2022. This represents an absolute increase of 94.6 and a percentage increase of 3941.67%. This significant growth could be attributed to the country's efforts to align with international standards, possibly as part of a strategy to improve the quality of its industries and make them more competitive in global markets. In terms of percentage change, both Tanzania and Mongolia have shown strong growth, with increases of 900% and 700%, respectively. This suggests that, despite their initially low adoption levels, these nations are making significant progress in implementing quality management systems compliant with ISO 9001 standards. For Tanzania, the increase from 0.1 to 1 is still notable in a context where quality certification can boost foreign investor confidence. Meanwhile, Mongolia, which increased from 0.5 to 4, is likely seeking to improve its extractive and manufacturing industries to meet higher international standards. Ghana, Cambodia, and Zimbabwe also demonstrate high growth rates, with percentage increases of 550%, 242.86%, and 229.41%, respectively. In these countries, economic and industrial development may be linked to increased use of ISO 9001 certification as a means to promote the quality of local products in international markets. Cambodia, for example, is attempting to position itself as an alternative manufacturing hub in Southeast Asia, while Zimbabwe may be aiming to improve quality to attract new foreign investments. In North Africa, Morocco has shown solid growth, with an increase of 212.50%, likely tied to the country's efforts to diversify its economy and improve the quality of export-bound products, particularly in the automotive and aerospace sectors. Tunisia has also seen significant growth, with a change of 139.58%, reflecting a greater commitment to ensuring the quality of manufactured products and services, especially for the European market. On the opposite end of the spectrum, some countries have experienced a significant decline in ISO 9001 adoption. Romania saw a drastic decrease, with a 56% reduction in the number of ISO 9001 certificates, from 100 in 2013 to 44 in 2022. This may be due to a combination of factors, including market saturation or the presence of other, more specific sectoral certifications that have gained prominence. A similar trend can be observed in Moldova, which saw a decline of 56.55%, and Malta, which registered a reduction of 69.20%. The latter figure is particularly surprising, given Malta's long-standing economic ties with the European Union and its well-developed industrial system. South Korea and Singapore, two highly industrialized and technologically advanced economies, also experienced significant declines in ISO 9001 adoption, with reductions of 60.28% and 59.39%, respectively. This decline could be attributed to the increasing adoption of certifications specific to key sectors, such as electronics and advanced technologies, which require more specialized quality standards compared to the more general ISO 9001. China, which saw a decrease from 58.7 certificates in 2013 to 34.5 in 2022, experienced a reduction of 41.23%. While this decline may appear negative, it is possible that many Chinese companies are adopting other quality standards, or that the exponential growth of certain sectors, such as technology, is leading to a shift toward more specialized and sectoral certifications. Nonetheless, China remains an important player in ISO 9001 certifications, especially given its vast industrial base. The United States, with a 37.14% decrease, and Japan, with a reduction of 39.38%, exhibit similar trends. Here, the presence of highly specific sectoral certifications may explain the decline in ISO 9001 adoption, as industries like automotive, aerospace, and electronics have stricter, more sector-specific standards that better meet the needs of those industries. Finally, Turkey and Vietnam have experienced dramatic reductions, with declines of 52.54% and 68.01%, respectively. In Vietnam's case, the drop may be related to a transition toward more specialized industrial sectors, while for Turkey, the country's unstable political and economic situation may have negatively impacted the spread of certifications. In summary, the data clearly show how ISO 9001 certification adoption is increasing in many emerging and developing countries, while it is declining in several advanced economies, likely due to evolving sectoral needs or market

saturation. Nevertheless, ISO 9001 certification remains an important indicator of commitment to quality, particularly for growing countries seeking to enhance their competitiveness in international markets.

Conclusions. The value of the observed variable decreased from 20.82 to 18.15 units, representing a change of -2.66 units or -12.81% between 2013 and 2022. Some countries have a value for the observed variable that is significantly higher than the average, such as Belarus with +3941.67%, Tanzania with +900.00%, Mongolia with +700.00%, Ghana with +550.00%, and Cambodia with +242.86%. However, there are also countries where the value of the observed variable has decreased significantly, including Kazakhstan with -65.45%, Vietnam with -68.01%, Malta with -69.20%, Zambia with -75.00%, and Russia with -78.50%.

	Country	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Belarus	2,4	97	94,6	3941,67
	Tanzania	0,1	1	0,9	900,00
	Mongolia	0,5	4	3,5	700,00
	Ghana	0,2	1,3	1,1	550,00
	Cambodia	0,7	2,4	1,7	242,86
Worse Performers	Kazakhstan	5,5	1,9	-3,6	-65,45
	Vietnam	32,2	10,3	-21,9	-68,01
	Malta	81,5	25,1	-56,4	-69,20
	Zambia	2,8	0,7	-2,1	-75,00
	Russian Federation	10,7	2,3	-8,4	-78,50

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